

Sustainable Financial Performance of Select Banks

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ABSTRACT

The paper discusses the CSR implications in the Indian banking sector, corporate conscience disclosure practices and their effect on monetary performance. 'Solvency' shows ability to pay its bills in the long term and 'Profitability' shows the ability of a business to earn profits in relation to investments. So, all these variables shows performance of a business in different areas. Previous studies show that these variables are correlated and if one variable increases or decreases, it impacts the one or the other. This paper throws a light on the CSR activities in a developing country's financial sector.

KEY WORDS: Corporate Social Responsibility, Liquidity, Profitability, Efficiency, Profitability.

INTRODUCTION

In the financial sector, CSR emerged as a hedge against financial scandals and banks' declining credibility. Nowadays, banks' role goes beyond monetary and commercial stability. The banking segment is a critical constituent in contributing to broader public external welfare. It includes a range of stakeholders—owners, administrators, investors, debtors, and regulators. The CSR definition and its related problems were adopted relatively late by this field in the corporate world.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Profitability is a firm's ability to make money from the investments. A business that does not make money would be unable to survive for a prolonged period of time. Liquidity is very important when it comes to banks, because it is the contemporary and potential threat that results from a bank's helplessness to meet its financial commitments when due. All these variables are correlated as per the previous studies. So, if a bank invests more resources into liquid assets it will end up earning less profits and if it is not functioning efficiently it will have severe implications on its survival. The present research examines the bank's profitability, and its effect on the CSR activities

that each bank is able to handle these variables well to prevent losses on its earnings. The primary explanation for this analysis is the fact that most CSR disclosure work has been performed in developing countries. Equally, research on CSR activities are ineffective in developed nations.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The widespread public amalgamations and social groups nurtured disgruntled with the widespread unscrupulous company designs and groups now not being answerable. Jones (1995) has claimed that businesses abide first-rate expenses, and its accompanying entities and individuals. Corporate conscience initiatives in companies endeavour to boost and extend social and eco-friendly things to do in such corporations besides larger governance concerns. It is worried with how organizations encompass these community advantage matters in their elementary enterprise processes (Sethi, 1979). Smith (2003) continues that along with corporate conscience in groups is a key attention area. Lee et al. (2009) agree with that the companies sketch their duties headquartered on CSR intentions, which includes social, financial and ecological duties, which are critical for turning into an appropriate corporate citizen.

Khan et al., (2016) in their study “Exploring Liquidity-Profitability Nexus: A Reference of Modaraba Companies” attempted to locate association between profitability and liquidity on a pattern of 26 Modaraba companies’ profitability isn’t influenced by indicators of liquidity, only CATCL had a large have an effect on over ROA in Pakistan from 2006 to 2012.

Owolabiet al., (2011) observed that the endurance of an enterprise relies on liquidity-profitability relationship in three exceptional enterprise sectors like banking, processing and manufacturing agencies in Nigeria.

RESEARCH GAP

The majority of the studies conducted had an impact on firms’ profitability and they were mainly conducted in non-banking companies and there are very few studies which have included efficiency and solvency for the impact analysis, because efficiency shows the firm’s ability to use its assets in earning income, but does it have an impact on profitability? Similarly impact of solvency on profitability will also have to be analysed. This study will analyse the impact of these three variables (Liquidity, Efficiency and Solvency) on profitability.

OBJECTIVES

1. To analyse the profitability and liquidity of select banks.
2. To assess the impact of liquidity, efficiency and solvency on profitability.

METHODOLOGY

The leading Indian banks considered are SBI, HDFC Bank, ICICI Bank and PNB. The ratios used in the study are Current Ratio (CR), Quick ratio (QR), Asset Turnover Ratio

(ATR), Loans Turnover Ratio (LTR), Debt Equity Ratio (DE) and Return on Net worth (RONW). The timeframe was five years i.e. from 2014-2019. The impact analysis was done using SPSS 24.

DATA ANALYSIS

Ratios of select banks

Bank\Year	Ratios	2019	2018	2017	2016	2015
SBI	CR	0.08	0.07	0.07	0.06	0.03
	QR	13.83	11.94	10.89	11.02	13.81
	ATR	0.08	0.07	0.08	0.08	0.09
	LTR	0.13	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12
	DE	15.79	15.08	14.24	13.87	13.34
	RONW	-3.37	6.69	6.89	10.20	9.20
HDFC	CR	0.04	0.06	0.07	0.04	0.06
	QR	17.48	11.19	14.51	12.69	8.55
	ATR	0.08	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.09
	LTR	0.13	0.14	0.15	0.15	0.15
	DE	8.58	8.02	8.25	8.00	9.36
	RONW	16.45	16.26	16.91	16.47	19.50
ICCI	CR	0.12	0.12	0.13	0.06	0.09
	QR	20.44	16.31	14.97	13.81	11.31
	ATR	0.07	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08
	LTR	0.11	0.12	0.13	0.14	0.14
	DE	7.28	6.58	6.86	6.64	6.65
	RONW	6.63	10.11	11.19	13.89	13.40
PNB	CR	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.02
	QR	22.72	28.98	28.09	24.23	25.19
	ATR	0.07	0.07	0.08	0.08	0.09
	LTR	0.11	0.11	0.12	0.13	0.13
	DE	18.80	17.39	17.28	14.51	14.48

	RONW	-32.85	3.47	-11.20	8.12	9.69
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Source: Annual reports of the select Banks

The current ratio of SBI used to be beneath the trendy of 2:1 for all the years of study, the place as in terms of speedy ratio, financial institution has carried out very well. The bank has proven a desirable overall performance in terms of profitability. The present day ratio of HDFC financial institution was once below the well-known for all the years of study however its quick ratio has been above standard, which shows financial institution has a higher liquidity. The profitability performance of the bank measured with the aid of return on internet really worth has been very incredible and high-quality amongst the pick banks. The modern ratio of ICICI financial institution used to be beneath the preferred of 2:1 for all the years of study, the place as banks quick ratio has been above standard, which capacity bank has carried out nicely in phrases of liquidity. The profitability performance of ICICI financial institution has shown a decreasing fashion in terms of return on internet well worth from 2015 to 2019. The modern-day ratio of PNB was under the standard for all the years of find out about and lowest among the selected banks. The financial institution has proven very best quick ratios for all the years, which potential greater idle funds. The financial institution has not carried out properly in terms of profitability, the return on internet worth has shown a poor ratio for 2017 and 2019, which shows banks overall performance has no longer been good.

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Return on Net worth	7.48	8.894	4
Current Ratio	.00	.000	4
Quick Ratio	16.00	6.164	4
Asset Turnover	.00	.000	4
Loans Turnover	.10	.000	4
Debt Equity	11.00	4.761	4

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.957^a	.917	.750	4.450	.917	5.492	2	1	.289

a. Predictors: (Constant), Debt Equity, Quick Ratio

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	217.504	2	108.752	5.492	.289 ^b
	Residual	19.803	1	19.803		
	Total	237.307	3			
a. Dependent Variable: Return on Net worth						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Debt Equity, Quick Ratio						

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	31.035	7.499		4.138	.151	-64.252	126.321
	Quick Ratio	-.763	.506	-.529	-1.508	.373	-7.197	5.670
	Debt Equity	-1.031	.656	-.552	-1.573	.361	-9.362	7.299
a. Dependent Variable: Return on Net worth								

FINDINGS

It was determined that SBI financial institution has proven a true performance in phrases of profitability and liquidity. The cutting-edge ratio of HDFC financial institution was under the popular for all the years of find out about but its speedy ratio has been above standard, which suggests bank has a better liquidity. The profitability overall performance of the financial institution measured with the aid of return on internet really worth has been very mind-blowing and pleasant amongst the choose banks.

The current ratio of ICICI financial institution was once below the general of 2:1 for all the years of study, the place as banks quick ratio has been above standard, which potential financial institution has performed properly on the basis of liquidity. The overall performance of ICICI bank has shown a lowering vogue in phrases of return on internet really worth from 2015 to 2019, which have to be a signal of worry for the bank.

The contemporary ratio of PNB used to be under the general for all the years of learn about and lowest amongst the chosen banks. The bank has shown best possible speedy ratios for all the years, which capacity extra idle funds. The financial institution has now not carried out properly in phrases of profitability, the return on internet well worth has proven a negative ratio for 2017 and 2019, which indicates banks overall performance has now not been good. The reason for reduce in profitability can be more funding in quick assets, which do not give returns. The study additionally located that liquidity, efficiency and solvency did no longer have a sizable influence on profitability. Liquidity had an adverse impact on profitability of pick out banks, therefore if liquidity increases, there will be decline in profitability. The study additionally discovered that solvency had a bad influence on profitability of pick out banks.

TO SUM UP

To assess the influence regression analysis was used in SPSS 24. The find out about did now not locate a big influence of these variables on profitability, but liquidity and debt fairness ratio had an adverse impact on profitability, therefore banks ought to focus on retaining a moderate degree of liquidity so that it does no longer affect profitability. CSR initiatives in firms strive to boost and make bigger social and environmental things to do in such corporations (Commission of European Communities ,2001). Lee et al. (2009) consider that companies outline their responsibilities founded on CSR motives, consisting of social, monetary and environmental duties, that are essential for becoming a properly corporate citizen.

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